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Research Article

PREVALENCE OF TYPHOID FEVER IN MULTAN***Dr. Muhammad Farhan Abbas, *Dr. Fariha Abbas, **Dr. Muhammad Sohail Asghar*****Rural Health Center Muradabad, Muzaffargarh******Tehsil Head Quarters Hospital, Kot Addu****Abstract:**

Typhoid fever is very common in developing countries like Pakistan. Salmonella typhi bacteria cause the typhoid fever. It is common in children and sometime in adults. Typhoid fever spreads mainly by the contaminated food and poor hygienic environment. It can also spread by close contact with infected patient. The common sign and symptoms of typhoid fever are abdominal pain, headache, high fever, diarrhea and constipation. The study was conducted in Multan and sample of 250 patients were collected from January 2017 to November 2018. The age group of the sample varied from 3 years to 19 years including both male and female population. Lab tests were conducted to verify the presence of bacterial strain. Treatment of antibiotics made the patient better in few days. Complications of typhoid fever can cause death but it is not common these days due to improved access to health facilities and medical treatment. The morbidity and mortality of typhoid fever is not alarming. Typhoid fever is a public health issue and it can be reduced by providing improved sanitation and environmental hygiene to the community in addition with immunization and vaccination plan

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INTRODUCTION:

Typhoid fever is not new it has a history full of deaths around the globe. Typhoid fever is caused by two groups of bacteria. The infection of typhoid fever which is caused by the consumption of contaminated water and food is due to *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhi (typhoid fever) or *Salmonella enterica* serovar Paratyphoid A, B or C (paratyphoid fever). *Salmonella* is a gram negative bacilli, facultative fever anaerobe. The sign and symptoms are not developed at once it takes time to appear after exposure to the disease. The patient usually experience at early illness high grade fever, muscle ache, headache, fatigue and weakness, dry cough, sweating, abdominal pain, loss of appetite, rash, constipation or diarrhea and some time swollen abdomen. If patient don't receive any medical treatment after observing all the above symptoms, the condition may get worse. The patient became delirious, exhausted, may lie motionless with half closed eyes the main state of typhoid, at this stage complications can also become life threatening.

World Health Organization published a report in 2014 and stated that about typhoid related cases in the world were reported about 21 million and death caused by the typhoid fever was around 0.2 million in the world. Among all the cases 93 % cases were reported from the Asian countries especially the developing countries. India, Bangladesh and Pakistan

CAUSES OF TYPHOID:

Salmonella typhi is a virulent bacterium which causes typhoid fever. There are many causes of the intestinal infection. Following causes are considered the main reasons of getting infection of typhoid.

- The main reason of endemic spread in developing countries is poor sanitation system and consumption of contaminated water and food
- While in developed world the typhoid fever enter through fecal oral route when their citizen travel to the developing countries and take the bacteria while travelling
- *Salmonella typhi* is present in the urine and feces of the infected patient and if he don't wash hands properly and work on food then he/she can easily transfer the infection to others
- Drinking water contaminated with bacteria *salmonella typhi* can cause the infection

CARRIERS OF TYPHOID BACTERIA:

Typhoid fever is treated with antibiotics and patients who got cured some time became the carrier of bacteria in their gallbladder and intestinal tracts for

years and are called chronic carrier although they do not have any symptoms of disease but they spread the bacteria through their feces and urine in areas specially where toilet facilities are poor and washing hands carefully is not a routine.

TYPHOID COMPLICATIONS:

Typhoid fever can have mild and also sometime severe complications one of which is bleeding from intestine which is due to perforation or holes in the intestine. This complication is usually appearing in third week of infection. The perforation in small or large intestine symptoms can cause severe abdominal pain, sepsis, vomiting and nausea. This condition require emergency medical care as it can be life threatening.

PREVENTION STRATEGIES:

In developing countries it is the major concern of government to provide proper sanitation, access to safe water for drinking, awareness about hygiene and also provision of medical care. For high risk countries like Pakistan vaccination is considered best way to control and prevent the typhoid fever. Vaccination is not consider complete protection following preventive measures can help to reduce risk of getting typhoid fever

- Washing hands frequently
- Drinking safe and treated water
- Wash fruits and vegetables before use

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The following research was conducted in Multan region. The patients who came with fever and having typhoid like symptoms were registered. Total of 250 patients were screened for lab tests and clinical study. From the selected population 150 patients were typhoid positive. The children were the higher in number as compared to the adults. The socio economic factors along with eating and washing habits of the patients were recorded. The majorities of patient belonged to Katchi Abadis and from under privileged area and remaining population were considered at higher risk of getting typhoid due to poor sanitation and unhygienic life style. Antibiotic treatment was given to the patients and enhanced fluid intake was recommended. Patients who started treatment at initial stage were recovered early.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

The typhoid fever is a public health concern and also it is widely spread in Multan. The patients who were having symptoms of typhoid were further screened and registered for research study. From the table 1 which is about about age group distribution it is clear that 72 % of the total sample belonged to the age

group of young children from 6 to 12 years. 20 % of the patients were having age group from 1 to 5 years. The patients who fall in the age group of 13 to 19 years were only 12 %. It is obvious from the results that the children who are not trained about proper

hand washing techniques, eating raw food and living in areas where condition of sanitation is poor are suffering more as compared to adults and old age people. Mean age group of the children was 8.5 years.

Table 1 Age group Distribution

	Cases	Percentage
1-5 years	50	20%
6-12 years	150	72%
13-19 years	30	12%
Adult	NA	0%
Mean age group	8.5	

Following graph shows that children are at higher risk of getting typhoid infection.

All the patients were recommended to go for microbiological test. Due to higher cost of tests all the patients were not able to get it done. Febrile illness episode with blood test results were as 68% of the patients from the age group of 6 to 12 years got

their blood tests and were having typhoid infection. 16 % of the patients were blood test positive and were from the age group of 1 to 5 years. The patients who were from the age group of 13 to 19 years were only 8 percent.

Table 2 Febrile illness episode with blood test results

Age	Cases	Percentage
1-5 years	40	16%
6-12 years	170	68%
13-19 years	20	8%
Adult	NA	
Mean age group	7.5	

The common symptoms in all the patients who were typhoid infection positive were as described in the table 3
Table symptoms of typhoid fever

Table3 symptoms of typhoid fever

Symptoms	Present	Missing
Fever	+	
Vomiting		-
Abdominal Pain	+	
Anorexia		-
Diarrhea	+	
Constipation	+	
Headache	+	
Perforation of intestine		-
Nausea		-
Rash	+	

The patient's socio economic status was also registered. Majority of the patients were from low income group and were living in under privileged areas and in katchi abadi where the system of sanitation is poor, drains are open and access to toilet is also limited or poorly maintained. The community especially the kids are not aware about hygiene. 18 %

of the population belonged to middle income group and only 6 % of the sample was from higher income group. The higher income group who were well aware about hygienic condition but got the infection because their workers who were dealing with their food were coming from infected areas.

Table 4 Socio Economic Status

	Cases	Percentage
Low income	190	76%
Middle Income	45	18%
High income	15	6%

Following graphs is the representation of the socio economic status of the patients having typhoid fever.

When the patients and their care takers were asked about their hand washing habits the response was interesting. 32 % of the patients said they never washed hand after going to toilet or washing hands before eating food. 20 % of the patients said that they

always washed hand properly after using toilet and before eating any food. 48 % of the patients said that they some wash hand and sometime forgot to wash hands after using toilet. Table 5 is about their washing hand habit.

Table 5 Habit of Washing Hands

Response	Cases	Percentage
Always	50	20%
Never	80	32%
Sometime	120	48%

When the patients were asked about their hand washing habit and use of soap or sanitizer for washing following response were registered which is clear in the table 6. Among them 84 percent of the

response was about never using soap or some time using soap. It means the infection is transferring to the people due to their dirty habits and their ignorance about hygiene.

Table 6 Use of Soap/Sanitizer for hand wash

Response	Cases	Percentage
Always	50	20%
Sometime	80	32%
Never	130	52%

The patients were also asked either they eat food strictly cooked in their homes or they are consuming food cooked from outside. 72 % of the patients were

eating food from their homes and only 28 % were those who were exposed to the restaurants or thailas food.

Table 7 Habit of eating food

Response	Cases	Percentage
Home Cooked food	180	72%
Food from outside	70	28%

Patients were also asked either they wash fruits and vegetable before use with clean water or they just use it without washing. 64 % of the patients said they never wash it and use it after getting from shop. 28 %

of the patients said that they wash it before eating and 8 % said that they sometime wash it or sometime forgets to wash.

Table 8 Washing raw food before use

Response	Cases	Percentage
Always	70	28%
Sometime	20	8%
Never	160	64%

CONCLUSION:

The prevalence of typhoid fever is common in preschool and school children. Awareness campaign about hand washing and proper hygiene in addition with vaccination program can help to reduce the typhoid fever from the community. The ultimate solution in eliminating typhoid fever is access to clear drinking water and improved sanitation in the high risk areas.

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